

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Stakeholders' Engagement Guidelines

Deliverable 1.1

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	5
LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES	6
1.0 INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS APPROACH AND COMPOSITION	7
1.1 Multi-Actor Approach	7
1.2 Demonstrators	9
1.3 Innovation Ecosystem composition and roles	10
2.0 RULES OF GOVERNANCE	14
2.1 Interactive innovation mind-set.....	15
2.2 Geographical dimension	15
2.3 Technical dimension	16
3.0 OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES.....	16
3.1 Identify	17
3.2 Plan: methods for engagement	19
3.3 Implement: when to engage.....	20
3.4 Evaluate and monitor.....	21
REFERENCES	23
ANNEX 1: STAKEHOLDERS' ACTIVITIES PLANNING TABLE	24
ANNEX 2: ENGAGEMENT TOOLKIT.....	25
ANNEX 3: REPORT TEMPLATE FOR STAKEHOLDER ACTIVITIES	33
ANNEX 4: CONSENT FORM	35
ANNEX 5: STAKEHOLDER MATRIX.....	38
ANNEX 6: DEMO WEB.....	47

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The first Specific Objective of TransformAr is to demonstrate the potential of co-innovation processes for **Transformational Adaptation (TA)** towards climate resilience in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. This is to be realised via **6 Lighthouse Demonstrators** (ref. section 1.2) within local/regional **Innovation Ecosystems (IE)**, creating shared ownership of solutions and increasing joint decision-making towards systemic change. To ensure the participation and active engagement of TransformAr cross-sectoral and multi-scale stakeholders from the local and regional communities, a methodology for co-innovation alongside multiple actors was put into place.

FEUGA, alongside VERHAERT, the Demonstrator Facilitators and Technical Support Partners, developed a tailor-made methodology to drive a co-creation process with regional communities and relevant stakeholders to the project, from local to EU level. The methodology proposed is based on the **Multi-Actor Approach (MAA)** concept [1], in order to trigger **interactive innovation** [2] across the whole value chain, whilst tackling demand-driven, actual needs of said actors. It is conceived as a matrix organizational structure with geographical and technical dimensions (ref. section 1.3) to address all regional and technical requirements.

The aforementioned methodology compiled in this D1.1 received approval of all project partners, and provides the basic procedures for involving Demonstrator communities composed of regional authorities, business, end-users... which need to be addressed in their own languages and considering their socio-economic particularities. The result is a *step-by-step* strategy that guides all interactions with stakeholders along a feedback cycle, upholding the principles needed for a quick and wide adoption.

This document outlines (1) the composition of potential target stakeholders' groups in the TransformAr Innovation Ecosystems; (2) detailed rules for the governance and decision making; (3) operational management procedures at local/regional level, with specific activities for the project; and (4) tools and guidelines for stakeholders' engagement needed to achieve the goals of the other Work Packages. An early draft of this framework allowed for initial encounters with the stakeholders and more efficient planning of upcoming initiatives.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CC – Climate Change

DF – Demo Facilitators

EnCo – Engagement Coach

EU – European Union

IE – Innovation Ecosystem

FT – Follower Territories

KCS – Key Community Systems

LD – Lighthouse Demonstrators

MAA – Multi-Actor Approach

RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation

RTO – Research and Technology Organization

SAB – Stakeholders' Advisory Board

TA – Transformational Adaptation

TAB – Transformational Adaptation Block

TSP – Technical Support Partner

WP – Work Package

WPL – Work Package Leader

LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES

FIGURES

[Figure 1: MAA principles](#)

[Figure 2: Demonstrators diversity](#)

[Figure 3: Innovation Ecosystem composition](#)

[Figure 4: Key Stakeholder profiles](#)

[Figure 5: Governance](#)

[Figure 6: TransformAr operational management procedure](#)

[Figure 7: Stakeholder involvement](#)

[Figure 8: Work Package links](#)

TABLES

[Table 1: Demo Duos and main contacts](#)

[Table 2: Work Package Leaders and main contacts](#)

[Table 3: Methods for engagement](#)

1.0 Innovation Ecosystems approach and composition

TransformAr's Innovation Ecosystems are arranged following the latest European Commission recommendations and a series of requirements pointed out by the TransformAr project partners. Among the cross-cutting priorities for Transformational Adaptation (TA) are Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) [3], Open Innovation 2.0 [4] and international cooperation. In addition, consortium members stated the need for social acceptance and public readiness for the adaptative solutions proposed in TransformAr.

Another aspect to consider is that this is a collaborative, non-linear project as its different Work Packages can be simultaneously developed and rely on each other for creating adaptative solutions and region-specific portfolios.

In this design, each Innovation Ecosystem makes use of a conceptual Demonstrator (more on this in section 1.2), a regional network for interactive innovation [2]. This local, practical focus allows TransformAr to create and test solutions by joining forces with the Demonstrators' critical actors.

With these concepts in mind, a tailored methodology has been put into place to ensure an efficient performance of this participatory process following a **Multi-Actor Approach** (MAA), which is described in section 1.1. below [1].

1.1 Multi-Actor Approach

Co-innovation is a core concept embedded within TransformAr, for it is considered the only way for viable Transformational Adaptation. It is also one dimension of the RRI roadmap [3], providing a basic framework for the involvement of end-users. Accordingly, the first of the actionable adaptative solutions offered by the project focuses on co-innovation.

As the Beneficiaries have already stated, engaging stakeholders entails facing several challenges in the form of mistrust, lack of motivation or readiness, cultural and socio-economic barriers, redundancies, cross-sectoral and multi-scale disarray, besides the gap between research and practice.

Practicing co-innovation helps overcome these factors by involving complimentary stakeholders from the very beginning of any desired solution, building up a sense of belonging, including them in **decision-making**, implementation and evaluation; therefore, stakeholders are more prone to adopt co-owned solutions that relate to their short-term, actual needs.

In order to co-innovate, it is essential to involve stakeholders from the very beginning, making them part of the decision-making.

In addition, a Multi-Actor Approach is needed for TransformAr to yield the multi-scale knowledge from various regions, thus proving its relevance for climate resilience. The proposed MAA allows TransformAr not only to bridge the expectations of the partners and the prospects of distinct local communities, but to root and give this project a second life, too.

Regardless of the topic, there are principles to follow for any Multi-Actor Approach (Figure 1). All must be upheld whatever phase the partners find themselves in – first contacts with stakeholders are the stepping stone for co-owned solutions, providing basic information while contributing to trustworthy relationships.

Figure 1: Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) principles [1]

Innovation Ecosystems mix these principles with a set of rules and the concept of an innovation broker [5], or facilitator, configuring a new model for knowledge transfer: **interactive innovation** [2]. By embracing a system that fosters interaction between multiple actors and community building, the process renders in time a partnership where stakeholders are empowered to a point where they are able to accompany the traditional top-down innovation with solutions of their own.

Along the lifecycle of TransformAr, interactive innovation is materialised through tailored participatory activities, cross-learning workshops, shared best practices and the establishment of communities of practice with an advisory body (see section 1.3).

In essence, Innovation Ecosystems configure a **mind-set** that affects all the steps taken afterwards, setting a common behaviour for all the actors taking part. Despite shared core principles, TransformAr's Innovation Ecosystems are complex environments, with unique physical characteristics.

Consequently, the Multi-Actor Approach distributes roles according to a geographical dimension and a technical dimension [5], fitting in the array of stakeholders, the link between Work Packages (WPs), and the facilitators who enable local communication channels (see 1.3.4 and 2.0).

1.2 Demonstrators

For each Innovation Ecosystem, a Demonstrator is set up. These territorial networks help develop and test their own specific portfolios of solutions and also the usable, far-reaching products and services that will conform the Innovation Packages.

Figure 2: Demonstrators diversity

There are two kinds of Demonstrators: **Lighthouse Demonstrators** (LDs or Demonstrators) and **Follower Territories** (FTs). The former co-create the adaptative solutions as project pilots and are at the core of the stakeholder engagement process, while the latter are selected to test said solutions. Follower Territories have similar challenges to those of the Demonstrators and are interested in following their TA process and solutions implemented, in order to start doing the same in their territory before the end of the project, and mainly after its completion: this is the case for Gjøvik municipality.

In terms of criteria, all Demonstrators have been chosen for their varying vulnerability and readiness to climate change across the EU; their geographical distribution; and their inner Key Community Systems (KCS), as well as their impact and importance for sustainable growth following the COVID-19 restart.

All Demonstrators are water-related in one way or another: climate risks to tackle in form of floods or drought; water as a KCS of the region for preservation, management or allocation; or KCS largely dependent of water use for agriculture, fishery or aquaculture. This relation is even stronger between Lappeenranta Lighthouse Demonstrator and its Follower Territory, Gjøvik.

A common water culture means that they can benefit from each other, replicating **best practices, interacting** and learning together (Task 1.4). The Multi-Actor Approach empowers the stakeholders within the Demonstrators to a level of co-creation and interactive innovation, obtaining unique knowledge and multiplying the immediate effects of the solutions designed. For this to happen, it is paramount that stakeholders have the means and participate accordingly, relying on **counter-balanced** figures to make sure their voices are heard.

1.3 Innovation Ecosystem composition and roles

TransformAr’s tailored methodology places a regional network, or Demonstrator, at the centre of each Innovation Ecosystem. Work Package Leaders (and their respective Task Leaders) are to capitalise on the knowledge from each of the six Demonstrators simultaneously. Other figures intervene depending on the circumstances, for they have an advisory role, whereas the remaining parts are permanently tied to their respective Ecosystem’s innovation process (see Figure 3 below):

Figure 3: Innovation Ecosystem composition

1.3.1 Regional Community

The Regional Community is composed of those actors who, by belonging to the Lighthouse Demonstrator or Follower Territory and their respective KCS, are subject to be engaged but are yet to be directly involved in the process of co-creation. They are not included in the Stakeholder Matrix (D1.2, Annex 5). However, members of the Regional Community should be part of the community building effort. They are included among the dissemination and communication targets at regional level, and may over time be contacted in order to provide information or to update their status regarding Climate Change liability or disposition towards TransformAr. More on this in section 3.1.

1.3.2 Key Stakeholders

Co-builders from a bottom-up perspective. They are representative actors from their Key Community Systems, able to generate knowledge and motivated to play a strategic role in accelerating Transformational Adaptation to Climate Change. Technical Support Partners should verify the effective role and influence of these actors within each Demonstrator. Key Stakeholders often possess previous tidings with the local partners which reinforces their trust and commitment with TransformAr.

At the same time, some of them may also belong to the Stakeholders’ Advisory Board, as described in the next segment. Arranged using the Stakeholder Matrix (D1.2, Annex 5), they can be classified into seven groups:

Figure 4: Key Stakeholder profiles [6]

It must be stated that the Stakeholder Matrix is a document intended to share updated information about Key Stakeholders, those who take part in TransformAr co-innovation process, as the project evolves and the community building renders more involved stakeholders.

1.3.3 Stakeholders' Advisory Board

The Stakeholders' Advisory Board (SAB) supports the engagement process and dissemination activities while strengthening the reach of TransformAr. It also ensures the sustainability and persistence of TransformAr once the project comes to an end. ACTERRA is responsible for the setting-up and management of the SAB in TransformAr, in close collaboration with FEUGA and Demo Duos.

The SAB is composed of high-level representatives among the Key Stakeholders from each Demonstrator (evenly distributed), who are part of the consortium meetings and are regularly contacted (at least every six months) using online tools. Just as the rest of the relevant bodies within TransformAr, the SAB embodies gender equality along with its variety of actors from the public and private spheres.

1.3.4 The Demonstrator Duo

These are the consortium members that will be responsible for the implementation of activities and the demonstration of the different steps at the local level. More on this on section 3.0.

Demo Facilitators (DF) embody the role of the innovation broker: they will coordinate stakeholder engagement in their respective Demonstrators, implementing activities for the different Work Packages, and empowering stakeholders. Demo Facilitators will be backed by a *Technical Support Partner*, constituting permanent Demo Duos.

Technical Support Partners (TSP), mainly universities and RTOs, have been chosen for their knowledge about the Demonstrators' challenges, contexts, and opportunities. In terms of stakeholders' engagement, Technical Support Partners are expected to provide Demo Facilitators with expertise and scientific competence, so activities are properly carried out; TSPs may occasionally be consulted about engagement approaches or personnel organisation if Demo Facilitators find their contribution relevant. Later on, each TSP will accompany the methodological development of the Transformational Adaptation process, and then be trained to support the Demonstrators in its application and demonstration.

Table 1: Demo Duos and main contacts

Lighthouse Demonstrator	Demo Facilitator	Technical Support Partner
Lappeenranta	LAPP - Olli Hirvonen	LUT - Risto Soukka / Liuliu Du-Ikonen
West Country	WRT - Giles Rickard	CZU - Tereza Hnatkova
Guadeloupe	ADEME - Marie-Edith Vincennes	ACTERRA - Stéphane Simonet / Rim Khamis
Galicia	CETMAR - Silvia Torres López / Lucía Fraga	UVIGO - Ana Bernabeu Tello / Andrea Ogando
Egaleo	MOE – Vasilis Rafail / Dimitrios Tzempelikos	NCSR - Stelios Karozis
Oristano	MEDSEA - Alessio Satta	CMCC - Antonio Trabucco

1.3.5 Engagement Coach (EnCo)

The Work Package 1 Leader, FEUGA, coordinates early efforts towards the stakeholders, acting as an Engagement Coach, or EnCo. **Óscar Bernárdez** will be the recommended contact for this.

This *overseeing* figure is there to ensure WPLs and Demo Duos are applying the methodology, establishing clear and feasible goals, avoiding overlapping and ensuring shared decision-making alongside stakeholders. The latter is directly related to **community building**, the form of engagement that must be realised before interactive innovation is attempted.

It is expected that the Engagement Coach will gradually withdraw and let the partners proceed themselves from community building towards interactive innovation; from then onwards, there will be **biannual meetings** to solve any issues that may appear, among other measures (see section 3.0).

1.3.6 Work Package Leader (WPL)

After consulting the Demonstrator Duo, they will define the suitability of the targeted stakeholder groups, how and when they are best reached, and the benefits expected from meaningful engagement. They will contribute to identify the activities and needs regarding stakeholder engagement, to set the Planning Table (Annex I) and update it at following meetings. WPLs act on behalf of the correspondent Task Leaders.

Work Package Leaders' duties towards the Innovation Ecosystem are further detailed in section 3.0.

Table 2: Work Package Leaders and main contacts

WP	Leader	Main contact
1	FEUGA	Nuria Rodríguez-Aubó
2	CMCC	Antonio Trabucco
3	ACTERRA	Rim Khamis
4	ADEME	Marie-Edith Vincennes
5	WRT	Laurence Couldrick
6	UA	Amalie Bjornavold
7	WATER EUROPE	Ana de León

 Any change in the individuals appointed as Work Package Leader, Task Leader, Demo Facilitator or Technical Support Partner responsible will be notified to FEUGA and the Project Coordinator, who will officially inform all TransformAr partners during the Consortium Meetings.

2.0 Rules of governance

The governance of TransformAr from the stakeholder engagement point of view is determined by two main concepts:

- In terms of decision-making, the **mind-set of co-innovation** drives all the flows from the bottom to the top.
- In terms of interaction, there are two poles in the form of a **geographical dimension**, following the innovation brokering concept [5] represented by the Demo Duos, and a **technical dimension**, where the WPLs and Task Leaders answer for the researchers.

These rules can be simply put by following the previous figure with added fluxes (Figure 5):

Figure 5: Governance

2.1 Interactive innovation mind-set

The rationale of the proposed methodology comes from the concept of interactive innovation, as explained in section 1.1. TransformAr embraces it by developing Innovation Ecosystems, aimed at genuinely and sufficiently involve multiple actors from the Demonstrators, in particular citizens and end-users; this is achieved by co-decision-making right from the start. It is not enough to rely solely on those already motivated and influential, the Key Stakeholders; TransformAr's engagement activities should be accompanied by community building initiatives as much as possible.

Interactive innovation is the main rule of the Innovative Ecosystems within TransformAr: it determines how exchanges are carried out between the consortium and the stakeholders, and how WPs are linked together, given that this is a non-linear project.

From the governance perspective, interactive innovation is expressed through a bottom-up flow that tackles the challenges faced by the stakeholders every day, thus attending to their needs. This is a concern for the partners and for the European Union as well. One valuable outcome is co-ownership, which is then transformed into **trust** and early adoption; stakeholders are more keen to develop and implement innovative solutions if their involvement is meaningful and, more importantly, demand-driven.

*One valuable outcome of interactive innovation is co-ownership,
which is then transformed into trust and early adoption.*

Interactive innovation is about constant communication too. Stakeholders deserve similar resources to those available to partners, for this brings a **sense of belonging** and trust. That is why the process entails structuring the information compiled in each Demonstrator, then relaying it bottom-up for a joint, accessible source that allows:

- Sharing broad, practical information and guidelines for Transformational Adaptation
- Cross-learning via workshops, frequent best practices exchanges
- Collaborative adaptation based on peer-to-peer learning
- Connecting innovation brokers and advisory bodies

Despite the common mind-set, the methodology still has to set the foundation for the work within the Innovation Ecosystems. For this, an organisational structure has been created with two layers: the geographical dimension and the technical dimension.

This system of innovation is the expression of the Multi-Actor Approach, for it bridges research and practice through the figure of an innovation broker, or facilitator, who creates the necessary conditions for interactive innovation to take place at each Demonstrator.

2.2 Geographical dimension

Each Demonstrator will function independently, though following the same methodological framework and exchanging best practices, representing nodes from which to meet the stakeholders, addressing them in local communication channels in their **local languages**, and considering their socio-economic particularities, needs and feelings prior to organising activities. This approach has been devised by considering the Duo Partners chosen by the consortium, as defined earlier.

Therefore, the Duos of Demo Facilitators and Technical Support Partners are there to ensure genuine local communication, community building and **stakeholder empowerment** for co-decision and, eventually, interactive innovation.

In short, the Demo Facilitator acts as a central contact point responsible for establishing local communication and empowering the stakeholders in each Demonstrator, while Technical Support Partners back them with practical know-how for the engagement activities.

2.3 Technical dimension

The technical dimension of the Innovative Ecosystem represents the operational link between the Demonstrators and the Work Packages.

The existence of a geographical dimension significantly affects the role of the Work Package Leaders, who embody the technical dimension in an Innovation Ecosystem. As they coordinate the research along with the Task Leaders, they will not approach the stakeholders themselves. Instead, the Demo Duos will.

WPLs must respect the bottom-up approach of co-innovation. This means that they can choose the approach and the stakeholders' profile, but then are limited to the **oversight** and input collection. Demo Duos are in charge of executing the actions deemed necessary by the WPLs and Task Leaders.

It must be stated that the figure of the Engagement Coach does not challenge the technical dimension, for its flexible role is only circumstantial and it is supposed to solely aid, and not intermediate, in the first stages of TransformAr.

3.0 Operational management procedures

Stakeholder engagement guidelines can be expressed as step-by-step instructions, balanced using a mix of roles and tools. The outcome of these tailor-made procedures is a clear timeline for activities within each Demonstrator; by following the routines proposed, partners should be able to integrate Multi-Actor Approach values into their own workflow while benefiting the rest of the project.

Operational management procedures entail an endless cycle that must be repeated for any activity carried out. Similar to other MAA projects, TransformAr's engagement is arranged into four steps:

- ✓ Stakeholders mapping and identification (section 3.1)
- ✓ Planning the engagement activities (section 3.2)
- ✓ Design and implementation of the engagement activities with Stakeholders (section 3.3)
- ✓ Reporting and follow up (section 3.4)

What is peculiar to TransformAr is that it is built around stakeholder input, and that is the main driving force for the partners to deal with. In order to preserve the health of the Innovation Ecosystem, Work Package Leaders must be aware of the fact that stakeholders are not always available or motivated to participate in activities. Stakeholder inputs need to be included in all steps as well.

That is why some counterbalances are put in place, in the form of actors (Demo Duos, Stakeholders' Advisory Board) and tools (Planning Table, Stakeholder Matrix). The Engagement Coach may help along the procedures, whilst also hosting **biannual meetings** with the Demo Duos and Work Package Leaders to ensure the methodology is perfected and properly applied, solve any conflict that may arise, and follow up on the activities (more on this on sections 3.3 and 3.4).

i Additional perks available for the partners are the Toolkit (Annex 2) with practical guidelines and the Consent Form (Annex 4) that is to be distributed to Key Stakeholders via [Mailchimp](#), an online platform with a centralised contact database that allows Beneficiaries to easily tag and analyse the responses [7].

The sum of all of the aforementioned elements provides a compass for cohesive and efficient engagement procedures:

Figure 6: TransformAr's stakeholder engagement operational management procedures

3.1 Identify

The first step for stakeholder engagement refers to the Work Package Leader identifying the suited stakeholder profile according to the desired input, by relying on Demo Duos and making use of the Stakeholder Matrix (see Deliverable 1.2, Annex 5).

The Matrix is a document that reflects the evolving influence of the Key Stakeholders from each Demonstrator -acknowledged using the Consent Form (Annex 4)-. The profiles there collected include their role within TransformAr, their possible contribution, and how they may benefit from the project findings. Therefore, the list and detail of stakeholders may vary depending on their active contribution to the engagement activities. The Matrix should be upgraded at least once a year to incorporate the impact of said activities.

However, engagement is not limited to co-creation alongside these already motivated and influential stakeholders, and may be directed towards the whole Regional Community in order to inform or persuade them to get involved in TransformAr. Community building is just as important in the long term, and should be encouraged and fostered early on.

Once the objective of the activity is set, a selection of stakeholders profiles is put together by the Demo Duos, using pre-existing and local communication channels (a practical means for trust building and data management compliance) to check on the selected stakeholders' availability and motivation.

The resulting group of stakeholders is then categorised (as in section 1.3) regarding their role within the Innovation Ecosystem and their current capacity –or lack of it- for co-innovation. This is the easiest way to later figure out the best engagement approach.

Local communication channels are a practical means for trust building and data management.

To recapitulate, there are different levels of stakeholder engagement in TransformAr considering the role they are expected to perform in the planned activities.

Figure 7: Stakeholder involvement

The **Regional Community** are stakeholders suited for Transformational Adaptation but considered external stakeholders: they are not fully involved in TransformAr, although may be the target for information gathering (surveys, meetings, interviews) or involved in dissemination activities. Through community building (workshops, trainings), these stakeholders might upscale to a level of co-creation and thus appear in the Matrix.

To be considered **Key Stakeholders**, stakeholders need to have already defined their short-term needs and actual involvement. Key Stakeholders are already recipients of relevant communications, regularly participating in activities, or even publicly sharing information about their participation; therefore, they are entitled to co-decide the solutions for TransformAr by taking part in policy briefings, discussions and joint sessions, or maybe acting as observers or in an advisory capacity. Key Stakeholders are the actors that will sustain the Innovation Ecosystem once the project comes to an end.

Last but not least, **Beneficiaries** act as internal stakeholders to the project, whether they are addressed due to their involvement on the technical or the geographical dimension (WPL or Demo Duos, respectively).

3.2 Plan: methods for engagement

There is no single method for approaching the stakeholders, nor should any method be considered separately; instead, multiple tactics may be used at once to ensure that the objectives are met.

Nevertheless, it is important to keep the focus and make clear expectations for both stakeholders and the rest of Beneficiaries, for they may try to combine activities with similar goals. It cannot be stressed enough that TransformAr stakeholders do not receive any monetary compensation for their time and possess different sensibilities.

Considering the identification procedure, the engagement method must also address other factors, such as the ongoing situation of the stakeholders selected, their motivation or availability. Before making any plan, expressed concerns must be handled by the Demo Facilitators, practicing co-decision-making. The early, continued feedback from stakeholders is paramount for the success of any engagement activity.

Once again, the Engagement Coach (WPL1) will assist Demonstrators in these engagement processes.

The early, continued feedback from stakeholders is paramount for the success of any engagement activity.

With all these factors sorted out, it is time to jointly decide on the precise approach or approaches- for the activity. Work Package Leaders have the last call on this, and it is vital for them to check the Planning Table (Annex 1) in order to avoid overlaps to guarantee the best outcome. Technical Support Partners are there to provide expertise and allow Demo Facilitators to carry out the engagement activity with the highest standards.

Table 3: Methods for engagement

	 Co-innovate			
Method	One-way engagement	Asymmetrical two-way engagement	Symmetrical two-way engagement	Co-owned solutions
Objective	Dissemination	Data gathering	Community building	Incorporate knowledge
Means	Demo Web, social media, press releases	Surveys, interviews	Discussions, policy briefs, trainings	Joint decisions, cross-learning workshops

This is a model similar to those of public relations [8], where a slight change on the approach can render quite different results in the short term. An asymmetrical two-way engagement does not modify the behaviour of the partners towards the stakeholders; however, a symmetrical approach is more prone to generating mutual understanding and thus positively altering the relationship. The key to **involve** is to foster neutral, balanced exchanges, where the conditions are agreed beforehand – this is directly related to the bottom-up governance within the Innovation Ecosystems. Nevertheless, there is always room to combine different strategies. Here are some of the possibilities:

Afterwards, the draft of the activity is to be included in the Planning Table, visible for the partners even when there is plenty of time ahead. Moreover, Demo Duos are expected to submit to the WPL and the Engagement Coach a first version of the Report Template (Annex 3) with the required information for the Events embedded in the **Demo Web** (Annex 6), a dedicated web space for each Demonstrator within TransformAr website created to fulfil the commitment of a transparent and trustworthy Innovation Ecosystem. The objective of the Demo Web is to enhance engagement with Regional Communities Stakeholders and capitalise on the efforts already done. Demo Web pages will enrich the TransformAr community by providing the stakeholders with the same sense of belonging, awareness and shared ownership, which are vital to co-innovation.

Demo Web provides the stakeholders with the same sense of belonging, awareness and shared ownership.

As accorded with the Demo Duos, the Report Templates (Annex 3) are to be filled in in English and the local language of the Demonstrator, providing data for the website Agenda and News as well (more on the Demo Web mechanics in section 3.4).

3.3 Implement: when to engage

After all the parts agree on the approach, Work Package Leaders step aside and let Demo Facilitators be in charge of implementing the activity, with the aid of its Technical Support Partner. The timing of the engagement will, nonetheless, be affected by the non-linear methodology of TransformAr. Since other Work Packages (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6) are to eventually engage stakeholders throughout the six Demonstrators, it is essential to coordinate efforts and get the best from each encounter, preventing fatigue in the Regional Communities.

Figure 8: Work Package links

The priority when establishing first contacts should always be to ask stakeholders for their **availability**, consequently drawing a calendar that also reflects the kind of activities they are willing to take part in. The first activity on each Demonstrator offers the chance to dedicate a special session to this initial understanding.

Even though there will be six inter-community exchanges of best practices between Demonstrators (Task 1.4), Work Package Leaders are responsible of checking on other activities while overseeing their own.

That is what the **Planning Table** (Annex 1) is for; FEUGA, as Engagement Coach, will see to it in the biannual meetings while also reminding of upgrading the Planning Table at least twice a year.

The Planning Table includes short-term, concrete data for coordination of early activities, as well as long-term references, which will be better defined over time to reduce pressure on certain periods and locations. Initial feedback is already in place to guide others in the process and test the platform.

From then on, Work Package Leaders -aided by the Engagement Coach- must coordinate the timing of the activities, accommodating their workflow with the ongoing situation of the different Demonstrators, and maybe merging with actions that tackle matching objectives. There is not a specific criterion for the pressure endured by stakeholders; Demo Duos are expected to empower their Regional Communities and relay to the Work Package Leaders the stakeholders' availability for upcoming activities.

Having identified a set of Key Stakeholders and Work Package specific goals, some activities were redefined for the early stage of the project, M3-M6, namely WP5 consultation workshops. This experience tested the partners, while also providing insights on how to improve this methodology and revisit the Stakeholder Matrix after its delivery.

 Some tips for engagement [1]

1. Choose a comfortable area and atmosphere to set the activity
2. Contact several times so stakeholders stay engaged
3. Organise study visits
4. Focus on commercial aspects that are of major interest
5. Accord beforehand on the topics to be discussed
6. Give easy access to all materials

3.4 Evaluate and monitor

TransformAr needs to take care of the stakeholder input, thus the setting up of the **Stakeholders' Advisory Board**, the body where influential Key Stakeholders from each Demonstrator come together. In the follow up of the action, these high-level representatives will *help* evaluate the bottom-up flow of knowledge and the community building.

Still, it is the duty of the partners to evaluate their own performance and the aftermath of the engagement. Demo Duos will do so forwarding **Report Templates** (Annex 3) to the WPLs, the managers of TransformAr's website (Water Europe) and the Engagement Coach (FEUGA).

Report Templates include internal use data (processed for research), an evaluation of the stakeholders' involvement and impact, and information open to disclosure; the latter will be made available in the website of TransformAr, and particularly arranged for the **Demo Web** news space.

Last of all, WPLs ought to assess the degree of success of the engagement alongside the Stakeholders' Advisory Board (see Figure 8, section 3.0), shaping conclusions that will be discussed in the biannual meetings and feed the next cycle of activities, beginning by the update of the Matrix.

The aforementioned measures ensure that lessons learned are put into practice, building a lasting corporate memory to guide the Innovation Ecosystems. Besides, being able to keep a close eye on all engagement efforts and their outcomes throughout the life of the project will empower TransformAr to quickly address emerging issues. It will also confirm whether the appropriate actions are being taken in a timely manner, following up on stakeholder calls, emails, complaints, commitments, and so on.

Evaluation is a non-finite task, and it goes beyond filling in the Report Templates needed for information gathering and website compilation. Each Demo Duo and WPL ought to register their perceptions in separate documents, as they can be useful to the Stakeholder Advisory Board and the Engagement Coach, or even for exchanges between Demonstrators (Task 1.4).

MANAGE CONFLICTS

Behavioural patterns and decisions made with regard to stakeholders, both as individuals and as a group, might constitute a risk. Some issues will arise regarding stakeholders' conflicts of interest.

Incorporating stakeholder identification, stakeholder prioritisation and analysis can make it easier to identify potential conflicts and manage them. Stakeholders may develop a lack of confidence in the project, either as a result of feeling that their concerns and opinions have not been addressed or that risks are not being adequately managed.

The process of stakeholder analysis and engagement may help foresee the risks and opportunities that a stakeholder can bring across the project lifecycle, and the impact of not putting a suitable strategy in place. Conflicts will be addressed preferably via the **biannual meetings** organised by the Engagement Coach with Demo Duos and Work Package Leaders, or alternatively through direct request.

A CALENDAR FOR OVERALL EVALUATION AND COORDINATION

- Six best practices exchanges between Demonstrators during Consortium Meetings organised by Task1.4 Leader (VERHAERT)
- Continuous reporting by Work Package Leaders to the EnCo on the results of activities performed with Stakeholders
- Bi-annual quality control and improvement meetings organised by the Engagement Coach with Work Package Leaders and Demo Duos
- Bi-annual update of the Planning Table by Work Package Leaders

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ANNEX 2: Engagement Toolkit

Available at the shared repository

Index

Context	4
Step by step	5
<i>Identification</i>	6
<i>Planning</i>	7
<i>Implementation</i>	8
<i>Evaluation</i>	10
Style guide	11
Contacts	12
Tools	13

Context

DISCLAIMER

Transformational adaptation (TA) is essential to reduce climate-related impacts on people, the economy and the planet. The EU-funded TransformAr project will create products and services to introduce large-scale and disruptive adaptive TA processes in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. Relying on existing successful initiatives, the project will address water-related risks and impacts of climate change through six TransformAr lighthouse demonstrator regions and communities that will test solutions. Transformational pathways are deemed essential for climate and social resilience to achieve rapid and far-reaching TA. Gathering 22 partners from 12 countries, the project's findings will contribute to the EU's strategy on climate change adaptation.

THEORY

This Toolkit is based on the Deliverable 1.1, 'Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines', a public document that contains all the theoretical background and the governance for stakeholder engagement. It is there that important definitions, such as innovation broker, Innovation Ecosystems or Multi-Actor Approach can be found. All the contents have been agreed and reviewed by the TransformAr consortium.

MIND-SET

Activities resulting from this methodology adhere to a series of principles for engagement. It is paramount to apply these principles from the very beginning, just as it is important to involve stakeholders from the first decision. Adopt this mind-set to ensure the best outcome of the activities you are part of.

TOOLS

Find below the procedures you should follow when engaging stakeholders. There are also tools at your disposal with links to download and interact with them.

Step by step

EVALUATION

- Stakeholders' Matrix
- Report Template
- SAB aid

IMPLEMENTATION

- Consent Form
- Planning Table
- Demo Duo responsible

IDENTIFICATION

- Stakeholders' Matrix
- Involvement Chart

PLANNING

- Methods Chart
- Report Template
- Planning Table

Identification

-
Objective
 Selection of the stakeholder profile(s) suited for the Work Package / Task desired outcome
-
Procedure
 Definition of the activity's goal by Work Package Leader / Task Leader – Preliminary selection by Demo Duo using local communication channels for the Regional Community and Stakeholders' Matrix database for Key Stakeholders – Demo Facilitator check on availability and motivation
-
Tools
 Stakeholder Matrix (annex) – Involvement Chart

Involvement Chart

Stakeholders' Matrix Excerpt

Planning

-

Objective
Co-decision on method and means, avoid overlapping
-

Procedure
Demo Duos use local channels to agree with stakeholders on the preferable method, depending on the stakeholder profile – Demo Duos fill in early Report Template for Demo Web feeding (Events) – Work Package Leader provides resources and updates Planning Table – Engagement Coach training and assistance
-

Tools
Planning Table – Report Template – Demo Web – Methods Chart

	Co-innovate			
Method	One-way engagement	Asymmetrical two-way engagement	Symmetrical two-way engagement	Co-owned solutions
Objective	Dissemination	Data gathering	Community building	Incorporate knowledge
Means	Demo Web, social media, press releases	Surveys, interviews	Discussions, policy briefs, trainings	Joint decisions, cross-learning workshops

Methods Chart

Implementation

-

Objective
Combine techniques for best outcome, set a working calendar with stakeholder and other WPs feedback, community building
-

Procedure
First contact to find out the stakeholders' availability and motivation (dedicated session or Consent Form) – Data Management acknowledgement via Consent Form – Demo Facilitator carries out the activity, Technical Support Partners provide expertise – *Optional* Engagement Coach coordination with bi-annual and requested meetings for specific coaching
-

Tools
Consent Form – Planning Table (annexes)

Implementation

Planning Table excerpt

Consent Form

TransformAr: Accelerating and supporting transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages
 Horizon 2020 EU Research and Innovation programme
 Grant agreement 1010330983
 Project coordinator: University of Antwerp – Jan Coolen
 Transformational adaptation (TA) is essential to reduce climate related impacts on people, the economy and the planet. The EU-funded TransformAr project will create products and services to introduce large-scale and disruptive adaptive TA processes in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. Helping us winning success of

Consent Form excerpt

Evaluation

Objective

Evaluate own performance, evaluate activity success and stakeholder involvement, Manage risks

Procedure

Demo Duos forward Report Template to the Work Package Leader, also WATER EUROPE and FEUGA, feeding the Demo Web (News) – Work Package Leaders evaluate the data gathered from the activity, and also the stakeholder engagement with the help of the SAB – Matrix updating: Technical Support Partners verify the influence and role of Key Stakeholders – All: internal reporting for next bi-annual control meeting organised by the Engagement Coach and best practices exchanges

Tools

Report Template – Stakeholder Matrix

A calendar for overall evaluation and coordination

Style guide

Beneficiaries to address stakeholders (mostly, Demo Facilitators) are still mandated to follow the style guide D7.3. Contribute to a trustworthy environment.

3. THE LOGO

3. COLOR PALETTE

Contacts

Engagement Coach Óscar Bernárdez (FEUGA) obernardez@feuga.es

Lighthouse Demonstrator	Demo Facilitator	Technical Support Partner
Lappeenranta	LAPP - Olli Hirvonen	LUT - Risto Soukka / Liulu Du-Ikonen
West Country	WRT - Giles Rickard	CZU - Tereza Hnatkova
Guadeloupe	ADEME - Marie-Edith Vincennes	ACTERRA - Stéphane Simonet / Rim Khamis
Galicia	CETMAR - Silvia Torres López / Lucia Fraga	UVIGO - Ana Bernabeu Tello / Andrea Ogando
Egaleo	MOE - Vasilis Rafail / Dimitrios Tzempelikos	NCSR - Stellos Karozis
Oristano	MEDSEA - Alessio Satta	CMCC - Antonio Trabucco

WP	Leader	Main contact
1	FEUGA	Nuria Rodriguez-Aubó
2	CMCC	Antonio Trabucco
3	ACTERRA	Rim Khamis
4	ADEME	Marie-Edith Vincennes
5	WRT	Laurence Couldrick
6	UA	Amalie Bjornavold
7	WATER EUROPE	Ana de León

Tools

Report Template

Adaptable to particular activity requirements by following the Style guide. Demo Duos forward it to WPL, FEUGA and WATER EUROPE

 [Download](#)

Consent Form

Consent Form is to be distributed by FEUGA via [Mailchimp](#), an online platform with a centralised contact database that allows Beneficiaries to easily tag and analyse the responses

Excerpts from a previous version

Tools

Stakeholder Matrix

 [Download](#)

Planning Table

Updated on a bi-annual basis

 [Sharepoint](#)

Tools

DEMO WEB

Each Report Template feeds the Demo Web. Within steps 2 (Planning) and 4 (Evaluation), the Report Template filled in by Demo Duos is to be submitted to the respective Work Package Leader and also to FEUGA (Engagement Coach) and WATER EUROPE (Website manager).

The Demo Web is a dedicated web space for each Demonstrator within TransformAr website, created to fulfil the commitment of a transparent and trustworthy Innovation Ecosystem. It includes Events and News separated features.

The objective of the Demo Web is to enhance engagement with Regional Communities Stakeholders and capitalise on the efforts already done. Demo Web pages will enrich the TransformAr community by providing the stakeholders with the same sense of belonging, awareness and shared ownership, which are vital to co-innovation.

Pre-release snapshot

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

ANNEX 3: Report Template for Stakeholder Activities

ACTIVITY NAME: Title of the activity (i.e., Stakeholders meeting at Galicia)

DATE: When (i.e., 19/08/2023)

LOCATION: Where it took place (i.e., 19/08/2023, Vigo, Spain)

LIST OF ATTEENDEES: Expand this table as needed

Nº	Surname	Name	Organization	Stakeholder profile

Stakeholder profiles according to the Matrix are: Workers, Syndicates, Lobbying Group / Funding Support, Insurance / Government, Policy Maker / NGO, NPO / Scientific Community / Climate Advocate, Environmental Activist / Private Sector, SME, Consultant / Other

AGENDA: Expand this table as needed

-	Programme
-	00.00h - Example
-	00.00h - Example
-	00.00h - Example

WPL INPUT/MINUTES Include here all the data requested by the WPL or Task Leader as agreed. Be sure to write down a line about the stakeholders that took part, their final number and predominant profiles.

WEB SUMMARY Write a title and a summary of the results, in less than 500 words, both in English and the local language of the Demonstrator.

Abstract in English

Abstract in Local Language

IMAGES Include the images taken during the activity or generic pictures from the Demonstrator.

ANNEX 4: Consent form

The TransformAr project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036683.

TransformAr: Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages

Project coordinator: University of Antwerp – Jan Cools

www.transformar.eu

Transformational adaptation (TA) is essential to reduce climate-related impacts on people, the economy and the planet. The EU-funded TransformAr project will create products and services to introduce large-scale and disruptive adaptive TA processes in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. Relying on existing successful initiatives, the project will address water-related risks and impacts of climate change through six TransformAr lighthouse demonstrator regions and communities that will test solutions. Transformational pathways are deemed essential for climate and social resilience to achieve rapid and far-reaching TA. Gathering 22 partners from 12 countries, the project's findings will contribute to the EU's strategy on climate change adaptation.

The benefits of TransformAr

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories. Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioural change solutions.

Massive resilience increase and acceleration of transformation adaptation will be fostered by clustering various investors, testing bankable solutions, and defining viable (non-)commercial exploitation strategy for the TransformAr solutions, products and services.

The role of the regional communities

As part of the lighthouse demonstrators, the regional communities of TransformAr, you can be empowered to a level of co-creation and interactive innovation, obtaining unique knowledge and multiplying the immediate effects of the solutions mentioned above.

We expect from you to be able to take part on activities and demonstrations of the different steps at the local level, in your own language, providing insights for the local coordinators of TransformAr. You will do so following a comprehensive and previously agreed calendar, using means adequate to your situation, in the capacity you see convenient and without compromise.

Form

On default, your identity (personal name and personal contact data) will be retained confidential

Email*

Full name*

Where are you from?*

Lappeenranta / West Country / Guadeloupe / Galicia / Egaleo / Oristano

What is your organisation?*

(Open)

Choose a profile you suit*

Workers / Syndicates / Lobbying Group Funding Support / Insurance Government / Policy Maker NGO / NPO Scientific Community Climate Advocate / Environmental Activist Private Sector / SME Consultant / Other

If you have participated in EU projects before, write which one(s)

(Open)

State your consent (multiple options)*

Receive information

Receive invitations to activities

Be mentioned on the project's social media and website

Your participation is voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw your participation and personal data at any time without any consequences. You have the right to refuse to answer particular questions and invitations.

Data Protection and Management

Project Coordinator (University of Antwerp) and Epsilon Malta Ltd as members of the TransformAr consortium are responsible for the processing of your personal data.

By accepting these terms, you allow the use of the information for the purposes of the TransformAr project:

1. Your personal data is intended for internal use of TransformAr and will not be shared by any means unless stated in this form.
2. The information gathered from activities organised by the TransformAr consortium will be treated confidentially, in order to report our progress regarding the Transformational Adaptation process.
3. Image and voice recordings from activities can be used for related communication purposes in the absence of an alternative.

We will keep your personal data until we accomplish the objectives explained above. When it is no longer necessary, or you ask for it to be removed, it will be destroyed. You may at any time exercise your rights of revocation of consent, access, rectification, cancellation, limitation in the processing, opposition, and portability of data, as well as submit complaints to the authority within the consortium responsible for the processing of your personal data, by sending an e-mail to both the Project Coordinator – University of Antwerp (jan.Cools@uantwerpen.be) and Epsilon Malta Ltd (bonazountas@epsilon.gr).

We will treat your information respectfully and in accordance with the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 (GDPR).

I understand and accept the terms

Main contact

Name

Organisation

Contact email

ANNEX 5: Stakeholder Matrix

Excerpt from D1.2

LAPPENRANTA Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
Ministry of Environment	Government		Delegation of the minister of ecological transition and solidarity - Environment, planning and housing
Lappeenranta: urban planning	Government (departmental)		Environment & sustainable development
Greenreality Network	NPO		Sustainable development, CCA
LUT	Scientific Community		Knowledge and potential valuation of water quality and water protection
The Finnish Association for Nature Conservation	NPO		Environment & sustainable development
Association of Finnish Municipalities	Public body		Development
GoSaimaa	KCS		Tourism
Saimaa Geopark	NPO		Environment
Regional Council of South Karelia	Government		Regional council

LAPPENRANTA Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
Citizens of Lappeenranta	KCS		Citizens
Lappeenrannan Energiaverkot Oy	KCS		Water management, waste water management
Rejlers Finland Oy	Consulting		Knowledge in infrastructure planning
Conservation association of Pien-Saimaa	NPO		Improve the suitability of the water and coastal areas of Pien-Saimaa for housing, recreation and other uses, and promote their ecological conservation
Raija ja Ossi Tuuliaisien Säätiö	NPO		Nature conservation foundation
Ministry of agriculture and forestry	Government		
FCG Finnish Consulting Group Oy	Consulting		Knowledge in stormwater management and water quality
LAB University of Applied Sciences	University		Knowledge institute
Laitex Oy	SME		Supplier of material handling equipment
LCA Consulting Oy	Consulting		Environmental expert service
Municipality of Taipalsaari	Municipality		Environment, tourism, Lake Saimaa
Municipality of Savitaipale	Municipality		Environment, tourism, Lake Saimaa
WSP Finland	Consulting		Knowledge in stormwater management and water quality
Ramboll Finland Oy	Consulting		Knowledge in stormwater management and water quality
Lappeenranta: infrastructure	Government		Knowledge in stormwater management and water quality
Lappeenranta: environmental department	Government		Knowledge in stormwater management and water quality
Etelä-Karjalan Kesäyliopisto	Scientific community		Knowledge in social, health, administrative and working life
Afry	Consulting		Knowledge in stormwater management and water quality

LAPPENRANTA Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
Business Finland	Funding		Government organization for innovation funding
Center for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment	Funding		Knowledge institute, environment
Salpausselkä Geopark	NPO		Environment, tourism
Luode Consulting	Private consultancy		Water quality and measurement technology
VRJ Group	Consulting		National multi-sector construction enterprise
Vahanen	Consulting		Environmental
Sensmet	Measurement		Water quality
Endress+Hauser Oy	Private		Equipment manufacturer, measurement, software and system products
EHP Environmental Solutions	Private consultancy		Equipment manufacturer
GWM Engineering	Private consultancy		Equipment manufacturer
Burkert Fluid Control System	Private consultancy		Equipment manufacturer
Vaisala	Private consultancy		Equipment manufacturer
Flowrox	SME		Equipment manufacturer

WEST COUNTRY Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
County Council	Government		Governs planning, local infrastructure
District council	Government		Local planning and infrastructure
Environment Agency	Public Body		Lead authority rivers and flooding
Natural England	Public Body		Lead authority habitats and protected species
Catchment Sensitive Farming	Public Body		Improving water quality through tackling diffuse pollution
Area of Outstanding	Public Body		Provide additional protection, including planning in high value landscapes
National Farmers Union	Private		Represent farming interests
Country Land Association	Private		Represent landowner interests
Fishing interests	Private		Represent fishing interests, value of recreational angling
South West Water	Private		Provide public water
Developers	Private		House builders and Construction
Westcountry Rivers Trust	NGO		Innovation and delivery of nature bases solutions
Wildlife Trusts	NGO		Conservation projects
Farming and Wildlife Advisor Group	NGO		Conservation projects in agricultural sector

GUADELOUPE Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
County Council	Government		Governs planning, local infrastructure
Conseil Regional de la Guadeloupe (Regional Council of Guadeloupe)	Government (regional)		Decision making and development of climate policies/action plans Development of transport systems, water management, electricity and energy management Funding of public policies
DEAL (Department of the Environment, Planning and Housing)	Government (regional)		Delegation of the minister of ecological transition. Regulatory role (development of policies & regulatory monitoring)
Conseil Départemental de la Guadeloupe (Department Council of Guadeloupe-as a department of France)	Government (regional)		Decision making role & development of social, economic and environmental policies Managerial role (schools, elderly cares etc.)
Conservatoire du littoral (Littoral Conservatory)	Government / Public body (national with a regional representation in Guadeloupe)		Decision making role on littoral
Organisation of Easter Caribbean States (OECS)	Government (regional-Caribbean)		Regional organization joined by Guadeloupe two years ago. Guide and support decision making.
Agency for Ecological Transition (ADEME)	Both Government and Support body		Guide & Support decision making Raise Awareness Technical and financial support for ecological transition
Agence Française de Développement de Guadeloupe (French Agency for Development - Afd)	Support		Active
Banque des Territoires/ groupe Groupe Caisse des dépôts (Bank of Territories, in the group of Deposit Office)	Support		Growing interest
Chamber of Commerce and of Industry of Guadeloupe Islands (CCI IG)	KCS		Its main missions are to defend business owners interests and improve their performance
Le Comité du Tourisme des Iles de Guadeloupe-CTIG (The Guadeloupe Islands Tourism Committee)	KCS (public body)		Provide support for various actions to influence the flow of tourists to Guadeloupe

GUADELOUPE Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
Chambre de l'Agriculture (Chamber of Agriculture)	KCS		Research and development, training, advice, and project management, and organization to defend the interests of agri-related professions at the territorial level
The university of the Antilles (Guadeloupe Campus)	Scientific		Conduct research Bridge knowledge gaps Raise awareness
Geological and Mining Research Office (BRGM)	Scientific		Conduct research Bridge knowledge gaps Raise awareness
National Institute for Research for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE)	Scientific		Conduct research Bridge knowledge gaps Raise awareness
Regional Group of Experts on Climate (GREC) of the Regional Observatory for Energy and Climate	Scientific		Conduct research Bridge knowledge gaps Raise awareness
UNITE Caribbean	Private		

GALICIA Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
Institute of Marine Research (IIM) from the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Research Center		Develops marine research
CIMA - Centro de Investigaci3n Mariñas depending on Regional Ministry for the Sea	Research Center		Develops marine research with a special focus to regional aquaculture
INTECMAR	Regional Gov. Center for the quality control of the marine environment		Develops initiatives on operational oceanography and against accidental marine pollution. Has implemented a complete control system that covers all production areas of the Galician coast
Universidade de Vigo REDE and GEOMA groups	University		Develops research and higher education: REDE: energy, innovation and environment GEOMA: Environmental and Marine Geology
CETMAR - Centro Tecnol3gico del Mar (Technological Center for the Sea)	NPO - Foundation		Interim organization between research, administrations, industry and education and training organisations. Training Department and Marine Technology Unit
IGAFA: Instituto GALEGO de Formaci3n en Acuicultura (Galician Institute for Aquaculture Training)	Others: VET Center		Vocational Education center in aquaculture, also in charge of the trainings for shellfish gatherers, depending on the Regional Ministry for the Sea

EGALEO Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
IASIS NGO	Non-Governmental Organization		Development of projects and services to tackle social and environmental perils
Panteion University	University		Training of future professionals in various social and political fields
Western Attika Developmental Association	Funding Body		Creation of funding opportunities for cities to flourish
University of West Attika	University		Training of future professionals in various social and technical fields
Commercial Union of Egaleo	KCS		Union of all shop workers in Egaleo
Egaleo Scout's System	Non-Governmental Organization		One of the largest NGO in Egaleo regarding youth and environment
Museum of Asia Minor Culture	Non-profit, permanent institution		The most significant cultural landmark of the culture of Asia Minor in Egaleo
Community Center of Egaleo	KCS		Provision of allowances in citizens, along with consultation and other relevant psychosocial services
Social Grocery Store & Pharmacy of Egaleo	KCS		Provision of necessary items for the for citizens on the verge of social exclusion and financial deprivation, including medicine
Region of Attika	Government (regional)		The governing body of the largest region in Greece
Municipality of Farcadona	Government (municipal)		A Municipality on the southeastern Trikala regional unit, part of Thessaly in Greece, with more than 13.000 total population
Municipality of Larissa	Government (municipal)		A Municipality located in the region of Thessaly. Its total population is more than 284,000 citizens
Hellenic Association of Positive Psychology	Research Association		Provision of training services and research regarding positive psychology
Youth and Lifelong Learning Foundation	Funding Body		Funding Erasmus+ projects regarding youth, with a possible extension to environment
State Scholarship Foundation	Funding Body		Funding Erasmus+ projects regarding adult learning, with a possible extension to environment

ORISTANO Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
County Council	Government		Governs planning, local infrastructure
Municipality of Terralba	Public Body		Decision maker (Mayor) - development of laws/regulations
Municipality of Guspini	Public Body		Decision maker (Mayor) development of laws/regulations
Municipality of Arbus	Public Body		Decision maker (Mayor) development of laws/regulations
Other municipalities involved in the COAST	Public Body		Decision maker (Mayor) development of laws/regulations
Regional Government	Public Body		Decision maker / development of laws/regulations
Local Action Group Linas Campidano	Public-private		Director
Local Action Group Linas Campidano	Public-private		President
Legacoop	Private – trade association		Regional coordinator
FLAG Pescando	Public-private		Vice-president

ORISTANO Key Stakeholders	Type	KCS	Sector/Area
Water Management Body	Public		Director
Consorzio Cooperative Riunite della Pesca di Marceddi	Private		President
S. Pietro Produzioni Agroalimentari S.r.l.	Private		Director
Cooperativa 3A	Private		Consultant
COOP. Produttori Arborea	Private		--
Sa Marigosa Società Consortile a r.l	Private		
Liverani Servizi Smart Geo Survey	Private		Owner
AFNI - Associazione Fotografi Naturalisti Italiani	Private		Photographer
LIPU	Private		Member

ANNEX 6: DEMO WEB

Pre-launch website screenshot – contents subject to change upon release

The screenshot displays a website page for the City of Lappeenranta, Finland, under the 'Demonstrator #1' section. The page features a navigation menu at the top with links for 'The Project', 'Demonstrators', 'News & Events', 'Knowledge Centre', 'Related Projects', and 'Contact'. The main content area includes an aerial view of the city and a 'Key Facts' section stating that the city has a population of 73,000 and faces climate risks like increased rainfall and extreme weather. Below this is a section titled 'Actions and expected results' with bullet points about urban planning and water management. A 'Partners Involved' section lists LUT University and Lappeenranta. Further down, a 'Follower Territory' section introduces Gjøvik municipality, Norway, with its own 'Actions and expected results' section. The footer contains the TransformAr logo, a navigation menu, a newsletter sign-up form, and social media icons. A small text at the bottom left of the footer reads: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Innovation action programme under grant agreement 101006663.'

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.